

Severity of Depression among Families of Children with Special Needs

Samanta Bishnoi and Renu Joshi

Department of Human Development and Family Studies, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, Haryana

Parents of children with disabilities often face numerous challenges in managing daily life and coping with the complex demands of caregiving. These pressures can create strain in personal relationships, particularly within marital and emotional bonds. Consequently, mental health problems including depression, anxiety, and stress are prevalent among parents of children with disabilities. This study aims to examine the severity of depression among families of children with special needs in the states of Haryana and Uttarakhand, India. The sample consists of 70 families of children with special needs residing in diverse sociocultural regions. Data were collected from families of children with special needs in the states of Haryana and Uttarakhand, India. The study employed the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) to assess the severity of depression. Personal interviews were conducted with each participating family to evaluate the level and extent of depressive symptoms. The findings revealed that a substantial proportion of families of children with special needs exhibited symptoms indicative of moderate to severe depression. Notably, all participating families in both states reported moderate or severe depressive symptoms, with none falling within the normal range or experiencing only mild mood disturbance. These results reflect the substantial psychological burden experienced by families of children with special needs and highlight the need for focused mental health support, intervention strategies, and supportive government initiatives. The findings further indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in the severity of depression among families across different sociocultural regions. This suggests that the emotional distress experienced by these families is not strongly influenced by geographical location. Rather, the results underscore the profound psychological impact of caring for a child with special needs and emphasize the urgent need for targeted mental health interventions and support services for this vulnerable population.

Keywords: Disabilities, caregiving, marital, emotional bonds, BDI, sociocultural regions, interventions

Mental health problems, including depression, are prevalent among parents of individuals with disabilities. Raising a child with a disability can significantly affect the mental health and overall well-being of family members. Parents may experience feelings of loneliness and social exclusion, particularly when their child's unpredictable behaviors or medical needs limit their ability to participate in typical social activities (Eltantawy & Husseiny, 2025). Caring for a child with a disability is associated with elevated levels of psychological distress among family members, particularly in the form of depression, anxiety, and stress. Parents of children with disabilities often face numerous challenges in managing daily life and coping with the demanding circumstances associated with caregiving. These pressures can create tension in personal relationships, particularly within marital and emotional bonds. In addition, parents may encounter negative or unsupportive reactions from others, which can intensify feelings of guilt. The ongoing responsibilities of caregiving also require substantial investments of

time, financial resources, and physical and emotional energy, further contributing to parental stress and strain (Gordeles-Beser & Inci, 2014). Studies suggest that prolonged psychological distress experienced by parents is associated with a higher likelihood of family disintegration, impaired family functioning, and adverse physical and mental health outcomes (McConnell & Savage, 2015).

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines disability as an umbrella term encompassing impairments, activity limitations, and participation restrictions, which may affect children (WHO, 2007). The number of children with disabilities globally is estimated at almost 240 million, according to a UNICEF report, meaning approximately one in ten children worldwide lives with a disability (UNICEF, 2022). The birth of a child is a major life event that involves structural and emotional adjustments within the family system and may be experienced as stressful (Pocinho & Fernandes, 2018). Advances in healthcare have led to higher child survival rates; however, the prevalence of childhood disabilities has risen concurrently (Cieza et al., 2021). Children with disabilities often require more extensive healthcare and supportive services than typically developing children, including rehabilitation, assistive support, and long-term care, which places greater demands on family caregivers (Priego-Ojeda & Rusu, 2023). Children with disabilities frequently need assistance to address their physical, social, and emotional well-being, with primary support most often provided by family members, especially mothers (Fatima et al., 2021). The continuous need for additional care, assistance, and physical support places a significant burden on family members, often leading to stress, anxiety, depression, and other mental health concerns. These demanding caregiving responsibilities can also

Author Note

Samanta Bishnoi, Department of Human Development and Family Studies, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, Haryana
Renu Joshi, Department of Human Development and Family Studies, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, Haryana
We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.
Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Renu Joshi, Department of Human Development and Family Studies, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, Haryana
E-mail: joshir41615@hau.ac.in

limit families' participation in social activities, resulting in increased social isolation and a more stressful life for parents of children with disabilities. Parenting a child with a disability is associated with increased psychological stress among family members. The demands of managing unpredictable behaviors and medical conditions may contribute to social isolation, loneliness, and a reduced sense of social belonging (Eltantawy & Husseiny, 2025). Parents of children with disabilities are reported to have a higher risk of mental health disorders compared to parents of children without disabilities (Chen et al., 2023).

Research indicates a significant relationship between parental psychological distress and caring for children with developmental or cognitive delays (Azeem et al., 2013). Pocinho and Fernandes (2018) conducted a study to assess levels of depression, stress, and anxiety among parents of children and adolescents with intellectual disabilities, multiple disabilities, or autism. The study examined the influence of parental gender, the age of both parents and children, and parents' educational level. The findings indicated that parents of children with disabilities reported significantly higher levels of anxiety, depression, and stress compared to parents of typically developing children. Furthermore, levels of psychological distress were positively associated with the child's age being higher among parents of older children and negatively associated with parental education level, with greater distress observed among parents with lower educational attainment.

Azeem et al. (2013) conducted a cross-sectional study to assess levels of psychopathology specifically anxiety, depression, and comorbid anxiety and depression among parents of children with intellectual disability (ID). The findings revealed that a significantly high proportion of these parents met the criteria for psychiatric diagnoses of anxiety, depression, or both. Gruszka et al. (2023) reported that parental symptoms of anxiety and depression were significant predictors of adverse mental health outcomes and behavioral difficulties in children with special needs. Additionally, 7.9% of parents of children with special needs met the criteria for current depression.

Research suggests that mothers are more likely than fathers to take on intensive caregiving roles for children with disabilities, frequently sacrificing employment and personal time. The sustained emotional and physical demands associated with caregiving can heighten mothers' risk of depression and related mental health challenges, potentially increasing their vulnerability to serious psychological consequences. Raising a child with a disability can create considerable emotional, social, psychological, and practical strain for every member of the family. Most research indicates that families of children with developmental disabilities experience elevated levels of mental health concerns, including depression, anxiety, and stress, often leading to a decline in overall psychological well-being. In light of these concerns, further research is essential to gain deeper insight into the severity of depression among families of children with special needs, with the following objectives:

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the severity of depression among families of children with special needs
- To compare the severity of depression among families of children with special needs across different sociocultural regions

Method

Participants

The study employed a purposive sample of 70 families of children

with special needs, including 35 families from Pantnagar and 35 from Hisar, representing different sociocultural contexts.

Locale

The study was purposively conducted in Hisar district of Haryana and Udham Singh Nagar district of Uttarakhand due to the accessibility of participants and the availability of a sufficient population of families of children with special needs. At both locations, a Master's-level course on Special Needs is offered within the Department of Human Development and Family Studies. Families of children with special needs are associated with the Department at CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, and G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar. These institutional linkages facilitated contact with families, and data were collected from participants in Hisar and Pantnagar.

Measure

The Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), developed by Beck et al. (1961), is a widely used self-report instrument designed to assess the severity of depressive symptoms and related attitudes. The inventory consists of items rated on a 4-point scale ranging from 0 to 3. Total scores range from 0 to 63, with higher scores indicating greater severity of depression.

Procedure

The research protocol, including the procedures for data collection involving families of children with special needs, received ethical clearance from the appropriate institutional authority. Informed consent was obtained from participating family members, with assurance that their identities and personal information would remain confidential. The objectives of the study and the purpose of the visits were clearly explained to all participants. Verbal consent was secured prior to participation. Subsequently, individual interviews were conducted with family members to assess the severity of depression.

Results

The aim of the study was to explore the severity of depression among families of children with special needs. Additionally, the study sought to conduct a comparative analysis of depression severity among these families across different sociocultural regions. Depression severity was assessed using the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), a standardized self-report instrument. An independent-samples *Z*-test was used to examine differences between the means of two groups on the same variable. Table 1 illustrates the distribution of depression severity among families of children with special needs across distinct sociocultural regions in the states of Haryana and Uttarakhand, India. The findings provide insight into the mental health conditions of families of children with special needs and identify key areas where targeted interventions and support services may be required. The study results revealed that a substantial proportion of respondents 65.71 *per cent* experienced moderate depression. Severe depression was reported by 24.28 *per cent* of participants, while 10.00 *per cent* were classified as having borderline depression. Overall, the findings indicate that families of children with special needs predominantly exhibited moderate to severe levels of depression. Notably, no participants fell within the normal range or reported only mild mood disturbance.

In Hisar district of Haryana, a substantial proportion of respondents 60.00 per cent were found to experience moderate depression. Additionally, 28.57 per cent of participants reported severe depression, while 11.42 per cent were classified as having borderline depression. Notably, no family fell within the normal range or reported only mild mood disturbance in this district. In Pantnagar, located in Udham Singh Nagar district of Uttarakhand, a substantial proportion of participants 71.42 per cent were found to experience moderate depression. Severe depression was reported by 20.00 per cent of respondents, while 8.57 per cent were classified as having borderline depression. The study highlights substantial depression

severity among families of children with special needs across varying sociocultural settings, underscoring the urgent need for structured mental health services and intervention programs. These findings indicate notable mental health vulnerability among these families.

Table 2 presents an analysis of the mean differences in the severity of depression among families of children with special needs across different sociocultural regions. The findings revealed a non-significant difference in depression severity ($z = 0.12^*$), indicating that sociocultural or geographical location did not have a measurable influence on the level of emotional distress experienced by these families.

Table 1

Severity of Depression among Families of Children with Special Needs

Families of children with special needs	Hisar (n=35)	Pantnagar (n=35)	Total (n=70)
Normal (1-10)	0 (0.00)	0 (00.00)	0 (0.00)
Mild mood disturbances (11-16)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
Borderline depression (17-20)	4 (11.42)	3 (8.57)	7 (10.00)
Moderate Depression (21-30)	21 (60.00)	25 (71.42)	46 (65.71)
Severe depression (31-40)	10 (28.57)	7 (20.00)	17 (24.28)

Note. *Figures in parentheses represent percentages

Table 2

Comparison of Severity of Depression among Families of Children with Special Needs across Different Sociocultural Regions

Dependent variables	Different Sociocultural Regions		z
	Hisar (Mean±SD)	Pantnagar (Mean±SD)	
Depression	41.29±0.19	42.32±0.21	0.12*

Note. *Significant at 5% level of significance

Discussion

The study findings revealed that a substantial proportion of respondents, i.e., 65.71 per cent experienced moderate depression. Severe depression was reported by 24.28 per cent of participants, while only 10.00 per cent were classified as having borderline depression. Overall, the results indicate that families of children with special needs predominantly exhibited moderate to severe levels of depression. Notably, no participants fell within the normal range or reported only mild mood disturbance. In a study by Wang et al. 35.50 Percent of parents were identified as being at risk of depression, which was notably higher than the prevalence reported in the general Chinese population. Xia et al. (2023) concluded that parents caring for children with sleep-related difficulties were found to be at a higher risk of depression, while grandparents caring for children who frequently experience mood swings also demonstrated elevated risks of depressive symptoms. Sleep disturbances are common among children with disabilities. In this study, they also found that 30.90 percent of children with disabilities were reported to experience sleep problems, including excessive sleepiness, difficulty falling asleep, night awakenings, and disturbed dreaming. The findings of this study revealed a non-significant difference in depression severity among families of children with special needs across different sociocultural regions indicating that sociocultural or geographical location did not have a measurable influence on the level of emotional distress experienced by these families. Eltantawy and Husseiny, (2025)

reported that the Z-test value for differences between the mean ranks of parents' scores on the depression inventory was not statistically significant. This finding indicates that depression levels among parents of individuals with disabilities did not differ significantly based on the gender of the child (male or female).

Conclusion

The study findings revealed that a majority of families of children with special needs experienced moderate to severe levels of depression in both states. Furthermore, the results indicated no statistically significant difference in the severity of depression among families across different sociocultural regions. This suggests that sociocultural or geographical location did not have a measurable influence on the level of emotional distress experienced by these families. These findings underscore the importance of prioritizing the mental well-being of parents caring for individuals with disabilities. Providing appropriate resources and targeted interventions is essential to help parents cope with the emotional burdens associated with caregiving. Addressing their mental health needs can enhance their capacity to fulfill caregiving responsibilities effectively and promote overall well-being for both parents and individuals with disabilities.

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